

Teachers' Well-Being: Basis for a Wellness Plan

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Abstract:

Empirical evidence has been presented by research to demonstrate the tremendous influence of the COVID-19 epidemic on teachers' well-being across the globe. As a foundation for a wellness strategy, this inquiry aimed to ascertain the degree of teachers' well-being for the academic year 2022–2023. Using a self-made instrument that has passed validity and reliability tests, 137 Public Elementary School Teachers from medium-sized urban schools in a District of a big Division in Central Philippines provided the necessary data. Analysis that followed revealed a high degree of teacher well-being in the study area. When respondents were classified and analyzed based on specific characteristics, the results showed no discernible difference in the degree of psychological, physiological, and social well-being among teachers. The findings call for school administrators to prioritize teachers' well-being by striking a balance between empathy and flexibility to adapt to each teacher's unique requirements, while also urging instructors to continue their pursuit of professional progress.

Keywords: *Teachers' well-being, wellness, COVID-19 pandemic*

Introduction:

Nature of Problem

Due to the significant rise in sick absence and employee resignations among teachers worldwide, regardless of cultural background, the wellbeing of teachers has drawn a lot of attention in recent decades. It is a well-known truth in the literature that teaching is a difficult and demanding job that frequently experiences stress, burnout, and a high attrition rate. The bulk of research, like that of Benevene et al. (2020), has focused on negative markers of teacher functioning; however, in line with positive psychology's mainstream, more emphasis has recently been paid to the wellbeing of teachers. Being healthy goes beyond simply not getting sick at work. Rather, it speaks of the profitable and well-functioning teaching profession. While well-being relates more to teachers' capacity to create a positive, dynamic balance between their resources and their challenges and demands (environmental, social, individual, physical, mental, and psychological), physical, psychological, and mental health refers more to the absence of impairment.

According to UNICEF (2022), it is crucial to make mental health and well-being a priority and to make a commitment to doing so when schools return. By making time to relax, plan, set boundaries, get vaccinated, change expectations, learn new skills, and value the ones you already possess, be kind to yourself, maintain social connections, get your body moving, and seek mental health support, when necessary, educators, students, and their families can benefit from having more positive energy.

These developments have put teachers' well-being at jeopardy by posing several difficulties, uncertainties, and stressors. Given the unprecedented nature of the present school interruptions and the ongoing need to adjust to new rules and regulations, stakeholders and legislators are keen to learn about the difficulties teachers are facing and to devise practical solutions (Gadermann et al., 2021).

This study was conducted to determine teachers' well-being specifically on psychological, physiological, and social aspect, as a basis for a wellness plan.

Current State of Knowledge

The shift from in-person instruction to emergency remote teaching in order to uphold requirements for teaching and learning quality has been one of the main effects of COVID-19 in educational settings (United Nations Educational Scientific Cultural Organization, 2020; Garcia et al., 2021).

According to Alvarez et al. (2021), it's critical to recognize that well-being is a multifaceted concept with a range of subjective indications. Some have to do with developing oneself and realizing one's potential, which should always be viewed in its larger context. Exciting results have been obtained from research measuring the psychological well-being of instructors. These offer recommendations for the formulation of psychosocial intervention techniques. Also, Wakui et al. (2021), emphasize that teachers who have had to consider returning to on-site instruction may feel anxious about the possibility of spreading the disease, fall behind or struggle to maintain the scheduled teaching schedule, and see a decline in the overall academic development of their students. Teachers' well-being is a complex construct, conceptualized as the absence of negative conditions such as teacher stress, demotivation, and even burnout. Teachers' well-being has also been studied regarding coping strategies, engagement, and recovery from work (Pöysä et al., 2021). Additionally, teachers' well-being is a complex construct, conceptualized as the absence of negative conditions such as teacher stress, demotivation, and even burnout (García-Álvarez D, Soler MJ and Achard-Braga L, 2021).

Cherkowski and Walker (2018), states that concepts of what it means to live a decent life are included in the definition of well-being, which goes beyond simply managing difficult circumstances. Divergent viewpoints on well-being frequently take different approaches. Subjective well-being, for instance, includes concepts like life satisfaction and the predominance of happy emotion over negative emotion. Psychological well-being, on the other hand, is related to concepts like having a purpose in life and having healthy relationships with others. The understanding of well-being is further complicated because terms such as life satisfaction are sometimes used synonymously with well-being in the research.

Hallman (2020) explains that it is not only their education that has been disrupted, but for many children, being out of school has also meant the loss of their sense of routine and community and, in the case of the most vulnerable children, access to nutrition and a safe environment away from an abusive home. Before delivering Benjamin Bloom's taxonomy of learning – remembering, understanding, applying, analyzing, evaluating, and creating – educators must thus first ensure that their students' basic needs are met, as best exemplified in Abraham Maslow's hierarchy of needs: starting with physiological and safety needs through to social belonging, self-esteem, and self-actualization.

Theoretical Underpinnings

This study is anchored on Dr. William Seligman's PERMA Theory of well-being that focuses on the five building blocks that enable flourishing – Positive Emotion, Engagement, Relationships, Meaning, and Accomplishment (hence PERMA) where there are techniques to increase each.

According to the model of Seligman (2011) (see also Forgeard et al., 2011), positive emotions refer to hedonistic feelings of well-being (e.g. feeling happy, satisfied, and happy). Attachment refers to a psychological connection to activities or organizations (e.g., feelings of fascination, excitement, and attachment to life). Positive relationships include feeling socially included, cared for and supported by others, and satisfied with one's social connections. Meaning refers to believing that one's life has value and feeling connected to something greater than oneself. Achievement includes making progress toward a goal, feeling able to perform daily activities, and having a sense of accomplishment. Seligman (2011) argues that these five pillars contribute to overall happiness, are important areas that people seek out for themselves, and can be identified and measured independently.

This theory sets best in manifesting teachers' dynamism and optimism as contributors to their well-being. It builds better teachers' performance in school and work, plus better physical health outcomes. A healthy teacher is a happy teacher.

Objectives

This study aimed to determine teachers' well-being in medium-sized schools in a District of a large Division in Central Philippines for the School Year 2022-2023 as a basis for a wellness plan. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions: 1) level of the teachers' well-being in terms of psychological, physiological and social; 2) the level of the teachers' well-being when they are grouped according to the aforementioned variables; 3) the significant difference in the level of teachers' well-being when the respondents are grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables.

Methodology

This section discusses the research design, locale and respondents of the study, data-gathering instrument, data-gathering procedure, analytical schemes, statistical tools to use, and ethical considerations.

Research Design

Looking into the nature of the problem, that is, to determine the teachers' well-being based on the psychological, physiological, and social aspects, the descriptive method of research was used. McCombes (2020) defines descriptive research as quantitative, though qualitative research can also be used for illustrative purposes. To guarantee that the findings are accurate and trustworthy, the research design needs to be properly constructed. A descriptive research plan can look into one or more variables using a variety of research techniques. In contrast to experimental research, here the variables are merely observed and measured; no controls or manipulations are made.

Respondents

The participants in this study were the 137 public elementary school teachers from medium-sized schools in a District of a large division in Central Philippines, School Year 2022-2023.

Instruments

A teacher-made research instrument was used for this study based on the purposes presented in Chapter 1. It was subjected to validity (4.87-excellent) and reliability (0.914-Excellent). All of them were interpreted as worthy and good, respectively. It is divided into two parts. Part I included the variables that show the profile of the teacher-respondents, which include variables: age, length of service, average family monthly income, highest educational attainment, and net pay. And part II was the questionnaire, which included the Teachers' well-being in terms of its psychological, physiological, and social aspects. Each aspect has ten situations, a total of 30 items, and was rated using the five-point Likert scale as 5- Always, 4- Often, 3- Sometimes, 2- Rarely, and 1 as Almost Never.

Data Gathering Procedures

Since the researcher of this study is a School Head of the location where he conducted the study, a letter of permission for approval was addressed to the Schools Division Superintendent (SDS). Upon approval, the researcher prepared a letter of request to his teachers as the study's respondents to answer the survey questionnaire and schedule a face-to-face distribution of the instrument at their most convenient time. Safety protocols like the wearing of face masks, physical distancing, and the use of alcohol were observed during the procedure of the distribution of the survey questionnaire. The gathering of the research questionnaire was by individual retrieval since the respondents were just controlled within the school premises. After answering the survey, the questionnaires are immediately retrieved, and the data are tallied, analyzed, and interpreted by the researcher to solve the problem with answers and come up with a valid conclusion using the proper statistical tools with the aid of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) by the statistician assigned.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objective No.1 used the descriptive analytical schemes and the mean to determine the level of teachers' well-being based on the psychological, physiological, and social aspects. Objective No.2 also used the descriptive analytical schemes and the mean to determine the level of teachers' well-being when they are grouped according to the aforementioned variables. Objective No.3 used the comparative analytical scheme and the Mann-Whitney U Test to determine the significant difference in the teachers' well-being when the respondents were grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher considered ethical principles by securing approval first of the supervisors and school heads of their teacher's participation in answering the said questionnaire voluntarily with dignity, truthfulness, and fairness. The respondents were assured of their confidentiality and not to disclose their identity or their answers to the instrument. Responsible discarding of the instrument, which contained the raw information, was done by the researcher.

Results and Discussions

This chapter presents the data gathered in connection with the objectives of the study and analyses of these data facilitated by the identified appropriate statistical tools. It interprets the results derived from the analyses.

Table 1. Level of Teachers' Well-being in the Psychological Aspect

Items	Mean	Interpretation
Compared to before the COVID-19 pandemic...		
1. how is your mental health now?	4.11	High Level
2. do you feel so sad that nothing could cheer you up?	3.54	High Level
3. do you feel nervous due to the inability to meet deadlines?	3.42	Moderate Level
4. do you feel restless or fidgety every time you attend meetings?	3.43	Moderate Level
5. do you feel that your situation now is hopeless?	3.42	Moderate Level
6. do you feel you did your best in class?	4.31	High Level
7. do you feel mentally drained from work?	3.54	High Level
8. do you feel like taking a break from your profession?	3.68	High Level
9. do you think you have better connections with your parents now?	3.94	High Level
10. how are you coping with the daily pressures?	3.64	High Level
Mean	3.70	High Level

Table 1 shows the level of teachers' well-being in the Psychological Aspect. The overall mean score was 3.70, interpreted as "high level." Item No. 6, got the highest mean score of 4.31, interpreted as "high level", while item nos. 3 and 5, got the lowest mean scores of 3.42, and interpreted as "moderate level respectively. This implies that despite the overall high-level results based on teachers' psychological well-being, they feel that they are still nervous about meeting deadlines, and their situation now is disheartening. This creates a traumatic experience since face-to-face classes are implemented despite the pandemic. The implication negates the statement that one of the major consequences of COVID-19 in educational settings has been the transition from face-to-face instruction to emergency remote teaching to maintain teaching and learning quality standards (United Nations Educational Scientific Cultural Organization, 2020; Garcia et al., 2021).

Table 2. Level of the Teachers' Well-being in the Physiological Aspect

Items	Mean	Interpretation
Compared to before the COVID-19 pandemic...		
1. have you experienced depression and sleep disturbance due to the increased workload?	3.58	High Level
2. are you still adjusting to the present situation?	3.61	High Level
3. were your concerns addressed by the school well?	3.66	High Level
4. are you still stressed with all these crises happening now?	3.66	High Level
5. do you still have a hard time coping with the daily demands in school and at home?	3.47	Moderate Level
6. is it better to conduct this type of learning now?	3.77	High Level
7. do you still feel depressed knowing that we will soon have face-to-face classes?	3.51	High Level
8. are you stressed with the way the school is dealing with school concerns and issues?	3.46	Moderate Level
9. do you still have students struggling with anxiety over this present situation?	3.43	Moderate Level
10. are you more financially stressed now?	3.46	Moderate Level
Mean	3.56	High Level

Table 2 displays the level of teachers' well-being in the Physiological Aspect. The overall mean score was 3.56, interpreted as "high level." Item No. 6, got the highest mean score of 3.77, interpreted as "high level," while item no. 9 got the lowest mean score of 3.43, interpreted as "moderate level." This implies that based on teachers' physiological well-being, despite its high level, this type of learning now is way better than during the COVID-19 days where modular learning was the mode of learning. However, it appears that students did not struggle much and are anxious of the present situation. They must have adjusted right away. The implication negates this statement because a systematic review carried out on teacher health in times of Covid-19 has found that physical, mental and social health has been impacted. It is relevant to mention that only two studies were found related to this. One was about interventions for the prevention of physical symptoms (Kayabinar et al., 2020) and the other about emotional competencies (Roman, 2020).

Table 3. Level of the Teachers' Well-being in the Social Aspect

Items	Mean	Interpretation
Compared to before the COVID-19 pandemic...		
1. can you say that your workload has taken much of your time for the family?	3.48	Moderate Level
2. how was your relationship with your co-teachers now?	4.18	High Level
3. how was your relationship with your family now?	4.31	High Level
4. did the weekly meeting with your parents improve your relationship with them as you get to update them about their child/children's academic performance?	3.98	High Level
5. do you still have recreation time with your family now?	3.62	Very High Level
6. are you more anxious of how your learners will feel when classes reopen on a face-to-face set up?	3.64	High Level
7. Do the schools' intervention plans help improve your well-being?	3.78	High Level
8. how is your teaching performance now?	4.05	High Level
9. how was your social life as a teacher?	3.68	High Level
10. does it affect your professional efficacy?	3.67	High Level
Mean	3.84	High Level

Table 3 exhibits the level of teachers' well-being in the Social Aspect. The overall mean score was 3.84, also interpreted as "high level." Item No. 3 got the highest mean score of 4.31, interpreted as "high level", while item no. 1 got the lowest mean score of 3.48, interpreted as "moderate level." This implies that based on teachers' social well-being, their relationship with their family changed now despite its high level, teachers' workload has not taken much of their time for the family. It seems they are just simply ready for the class and tasks ahead. The implication affirms that teachers who have faced the prospect of going back to onsite teaching and have experienced anxiety about contagion risk as well as falling behind or having difficulty keeping up with the planned teaching schedule and overall student progress (Wakui et al., 2021).

Table 4. Level of the Teachers' Well-being in the Psychological Aspect When Grouped According to Age

Items	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
Compared to before the COVID-19 pandemic...				
1. how is your mental health now?	4.00	High Level	4.22	High Level
2. do you feel so sad that nothing could cheer you up?	3.57	High Level	3.52	High Level
3. do you feel nervous due to inability to meet deadlines?	3.40	Moderate Level	3.43	Moderate Level
4. do you feel restless or fidgety every time you attend to meetings?	3.33	Moderate Level	3.52	High Level
5. do you feel that your situation now is hopeless?	3.43	Moderate Level	3.40	Moderate Level
6. do you feel you did your best in class?	4.22	High Level	4.39	High Level
7. do you feel mentally drained with work?	3.50	High Level	3.59	High Level
8. do you feel like taking a break from your profession?	3.71	High Level	3.66	High Level
9. do you think you have better connections with your parents now?	4.04	High Level	3.85	High Level
10. how are you coping with the daily pressures?	3.66	High Level	3.61	High Level
Mean	3.69	High Level	3.72	High Level

Table 4 presents the level of teachers' well-being in the Psychological Aspect when grouped according to age. The overall mean scores were 3.69 among younger teacher respondents, while 3.72 among the older group both interpreted as "high level." Item No. 6 got the highest mean scores of 4.22 and 4.39 to both age groups, interpreted as "high level," while item nos. 4 and 5 got the lowest mean scores of 3.33 and 3.40 interpreted as "moderate level" respectively. This implies that teachers may generally feel that they are giving their best in class, but the younger age group obviously shows their true nature by being restless or fidgety in meetings, while the older group feels that their situation now is hopeless. The implication confirms the above statement that teachers' well-being is a complex construct, which has been conceptualized as the absence of negative conditions such as teacher's stress, demotivation and even burnout (García-Álvarez D, Soler MJ and Achard-Braga L, 2021).

Table 5. Level of the Teachers' Well-being in the Psychological Aspect When Grouped According to Length of Service

Items	Shorter		Longer	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
Compared to before the COVID-19 pandemic...				
1. how is your mental health now?	3.98	High Level	4.23	High Level
2. do you feel so sad that nothing could cheer you up?	3.60	High Level	3.49	Moderate Level
3. do you feel nervous due to inability to meet deadlines?	3.45	Moderate Level	3.39	Moderate Level
4. do you feel restless or fidgety every time you attend to meetings?	3.42	Moderate Level	3.43	Moderate Level
5. do you feel that your situation now is hopeless?	3.40	Moderate Level	3.43	Moderate Level
6. do you feel you did your best in class?	4.32	High Level	4.30	High Level
7. do you feel mentally drained with work?	3.64	High Level	3.46	Moderate Level
8. do you feel like taking a break from your profession?	3.76	High Level	3.61	High Level
9. do you think you have better connections with your parents now?	4.01	High Level	3.89	High Level
10. how are you coping with the daily pressures?	3.71	High Level	3.57	High Level
Mean	3.73	High Level	3.68	High Level

Table 5 shows the level of teachers' well-being in the Psychological Aspect when grouped according to length of service. The overall mean scores were 3.73 among the shorter tenured group and 3.68 from the longer tenured group, both interpreted as "high level." Item No. 6 got the highest mean score of 4.32 and 4.30 to both tenured groups, interpreted as "high level," while item no. 5 obtained the lowest mean score of 3.39 both interpreted as "moderate level." The results imply that teachers believe that they show their best in class; however, those who have been in school for less than 19 years feel that their situation now is hopeless, but teachers who have been there for nearly two decades and more are still stressed when they do not get to submit their reports on time which affects their well-being. The results confirm with Cherkowski and Walker (2018) who mentioned that well-being is about more than coping with negative situations – it also includes ideas about what it means to live a good life.

Table 6. Level of the Teachers' Well-being in the Psychological Aspect When Grouped According to Average Family Monthly Income

Items	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
Compared to before the COVID-19 pandemic...				
1. how is your mental health now?	4.00	High Level	4.23	High Level
2. do you feel so sad that nothing could cheer you up?	3.47	Moderate Level	3.62	High Level
3. do you feel nervous due to inability to meet deadlines?	3.42	Moderate Level	3.42	Moderate Level
4. do you feel restless or fidgety every time you attend to meetings?	3.35	Moderate Level	3.50	High Level
5. do you feel that your situation now is hopeless?	3.45	Moderate Level	3.39	Moderate Level
6. do you feel you did your best in class?	4.26	High Level	4.36	High Level
7. do you feel mentally drained with work?	3.51	High Level	3.57	High Level
8. do you feel like taking a break from your profession?	3.70	High Level	3.66	High Level
9. do you think you have better connections with your parents now?	3.94	High Level	3.95	High Level
10. how are you coping with the daily pressures?	3.55	High Level	3.72	High Level
Mean	3.66	High Level	3.74	High Level

Table 6 displays the level of teachers' well-being in the Psychological Aspect when grouped according to average family monthly income. The overall mean scores were 3.66 among the lower income group and 3.74 from the higher income group, both interpreted as "high level." Item No. 6 got the highest mean score of 4.26 and 4.36 to both lower and higher income teacher respondents, interpreted as "high level." Yet, item no. 4 obtained the lowest mean score of 3.35 among the lower income teachers and 3.39 mean score in item no. 5 to among the higher income group both interpreted as "moderate level." The results imply that teachers are consistent with their reaction towards answer on doing their best however, may feel fidgety and hopeless in their current condition. This is probably because of the bulk of work they are facing each day. The implication confirms with inquirer.net when "Our teachers' concerns go beyond education. We should invest in this profession in order to build our education system as a bastion of knowledge and hope for our future generations" (Yu, 2023).

Table 7. Level of the Teachers' Well-being in the Psychological Aspect When Grouped According to Highest Educational Attainment

Items	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
Compared to before the COVID-19 pandemic...				
1. how is your mental health now?	4.11	High Level	4.11	High Level
2. do you feel so sad that nothing could cheer you up?	3.43	Moderate Level	3.66	High Level
3. do you feel nervous due to inability to meet deadlines?	3.47	Moderate Level	3.36	Moderate Level
4. do you feel restless or fidgety every time you attend to meetings?	3.52	High Level	3.33	Moderate Level
5. do you feel that your situation now is hopeless?	3.53	High Level	3.30	Moderate Level
6. do you feel you did your best in class?	4.33	High Level	4.29	High Level
7. do you feel mentally drained with work?	3.65	High Level	3.44	Moderate Level
8. do you feel like taking a break from your profession?	3.68	High Level	3.69	High Level
9. do you think you have better connections with your parents now?	3.95	High Level	3.94	High Level
10. how are you coping with the daily pressures?	3.68	High Level	3.60	High Level
Mean	3.73	High Level	3.67	High Level

Table 7 exhibits the level of teachers' well-being in the Psychological Aspect when grouped according to highest educational attainment. The overall mean scores were 3.73 among the lower education achieved group and 3.67 from the higher education achieved group, both interpreted as "high level." Item No. got the highest mean score of 4.33 and 4.29 to both lower and higher education achieved groups, interpreted as "high level." However, item no. 2, obtained the lowest mean score of 3.43 among the lower education achieved group, and item no. 5 among the higher education achieved group both interpreted as "moderate level." The results imply that teachers obviously manifested that they show their superlative performance in class but may need to cheer them up so as not to make them feel hopeless in their situation. The implication confirms with Cherkowski and Walker (2018) who explains that subjective well-being encompasses ideas such as life satisfaction and the presence of positive emotion more frequently than negative emotion, while psychological wellbeing is concerned with ideas such as purpose in life and positive relationships with others.

Table 8. Level of the Teachers' Well-being in the Physiological Aspect When Grouped According to Age

Items	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
Compared to before the COVID-19 pandemic...				
1. have you experienced depression and sleep disturbance due to the increased workload?	3.50	High Level	3.66	High Level
2. are you still adjusting to the present situation?	3.56	High Level	3.66	High Level
3. were your concerns addressed by the school well?	3.63	High Level	3.69	High Level
4. are you still stressed with all these crises happening now?	3.62	High Level	3.70	High Level
5. do you still have a hard time coping with the daily demands in school and at home?	3.42	Moderate Level	3.52	High Level
6. is it better to conduct this type of learning now?	3.75	High Level	3.78	High Level
7. do you still feel depressed knowing that we will soon have face-to-face classes?	3.57	High Level	3.45	Moderate Level
8. are you stressed with the way the school is dealing with school concerns and issues?	3.43	Moderate Level	3.49	Moderate Level
9. do you still have students struggling with anxiety over this present situation?	3.48	Moderate Level	3.38	Moderate Level
10. are you more financially stressed now?	3.46	Moderate Level	3.46	Moderate Level
Mean	3.54	High Level	3.58	High Level

Table 8 presents the level of teachers' well-being in the Physiological Aspect when grouped according to age. The overall mean scores were 3.54 among the younger teacher respondents, while 3.58 among the older group both interpreted as "high level." Item no. 6 got the highest mean scores of 3.75 and 3.78 to both age groups, interpreted as "high level," while item no. 5 got the lowest mean score of 3.42 among younger teacher respondents and item no. 9 with the lowest mean score of 3.38 both interpreted as "moderate level" respectively. This implies that teachers physiologically felt that this type of learning used now is better but they have a hard time coping with the daily demands of both home and school and are stressed with students who are struggling with anxiety over this present situation. The implication confirms that in Dayagbil et al. (2021) study that teacher'

well-being and contentment are of primary importance in teaching effectiveness. Well-being would be significantly and positively correlated with contentment.

Table 9. Level of the Teachers' Well-being in the Physiological Aspect When Grouped According to Length of Service

Items	Shorter		Longer	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
Compared to before the COVID-19 pandemic...				
1. have you experienced depression and sleep disturbance due to the increased workload?	3.56	High Level	3.60	High Level
2. are you still adjusting to the present situation?	3.65	High Level	3.57	High Level
3. were your concerns addressed by the school well?	3.60	Moderate Level	3.71	High Level
4. are you still stressed with all these crises happening now?	3.62	High Level	3.69	High Level
5. do you still have a hard time coping with the daily demands in school and at home?	3.48	Moderate Level	3.46	Moderate Level
6. is it better to conduct this type of learning now?	3.79	High Level	3.75	High Level
7. do you still feel depressed knowing that we will soon have face-to-face classes?	3.54	High Level	3.47	Moderate Level
8. are you stressed with the way the school is dealing with school concerns and issues?	3.45	Moderate Level	3.47	Moderate Level
9. do you still have students struggling with anxiety over this present situation?	3.48	Moderate Level	3.38	Moderate Level
10. are you more financially stressed now?	3.50	High Level	3.43	Moderate Level
Mean	3.57	High Level	3.55	High Level

Table 9 shows the level of teachers' well-being in the Physiological Aspect when grouped according to length of service. The overall mean scores were 3.57 among the shorter tenured group and 3.55 from the longer tenured group, both interpreted as "high level." Item No. 6 again got the highest mean scores of 3.79 and 3.75 to both tenured groups, interpreted as "high level." Item no. 8 got the lowest mean score of 3.45 among the shorter tenured group while among the longer tenured group; item no. 9 also obtained the lowest mean score of 3.38 both interpreted as "moderate level." The results imply that teachers find the conduct of this type of learning now as fitting but stressed with the way the school is dealing its issues and in knowing that students struggle and anxious over their present situation that may affects their well-being. The implication was confirmed by Dayagbil et al. (2021) in their survey, which included the type of home environment the students have to assess factors that influence their difficulty. Students were asked whether their home learning environment is conducive to learning or not. That as teaching continuity was made possible through online modality and other home-based tasks; they still had difficulty complying with the requirements of the course.

Table 10 . Level of the Teachers' Well-being in the Physiological Aspect When Grouped According to Average Family Monthly Income

Items	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
Compared to before the COVID-19 pandemic...				
1. have you experienced depression and sleep disturbance due to the increased workload?	3.54	High Level	3.62	High Level
2. are you still adjusting to the present situation?	3.60	High Level	3.62	High Level
3. were your concerns addressed by the school well?	3.64	High Level	3.68	High Level
4. are you still stressed with all these crises happening now?	3.66	High Level	3.66	High Level
5. do you still have a hard time coping with the daily demands in school and at home?	3.47	Moderate Level	3.47	Moderate Level
6. is it better to conduct this type of learning now?	3.69	High Level	3.85	High Level
7. do you still feel depressed knowing that we will soon have face-to-face classes?	3.55	High Level	3.46	Moderate Level
8. are you stressed with the way the school is dealing with school concerns and issues?	3.42	Moderate Level	3.50	High Level
9. do you still have students struggling with anxiety over this present situation?	3.41	Moderate Level	3.44	Moderate Level
10. are you more financially stressed now?	3.45	Moderate Level	3.47	Moderate Level
Mean	3.54	High Level	3.58	High Level

Table 10 displays the level of teachers' well-being in the Physiological Aspect when grouped according to average family monthly income. The overall mean scores were 3.54 among the lower income group and 3.58 from the higher income group, both interpreted as "high level." Item No. 6 continually got the highest mean score of 3.69 and 3.85 to both lower and higher income teacher respondents, interpreted as "high level." Yet, item no. 9 obtained the lowest mean scores of 3.41 and 3.44 among the lower and higher income teachers both interpreted as "moderate level." The results imply that teachers show a positive reaction towards the type of learning they are getting now however, students are the ones struggling with this kind of learning situation. The implication confirms with one study related to the well-being of music teachers in the United States has been examined using the PERMA model, where findings indicated significantly lower levels of overall well-being, in addition to significantly higher levels of depression than published norms (Miksza et al., 2021; Parkes et al., 2021).

Table 11. *Level of the Teachers' Well-being in the Physiological Aspect When Grouped According to Highest Educational Attainment*

Items	Lower	Interpretation	Higher	Interpretation
	Mean		Mean	
Compared to before the COVID-19 pandemic...				
1. have you experienced depression and sleep disturbance due to the increased workload?	3.65	High Level	3.51	High Level
2. are you still adjusting to the present situation?	3.72	High Level	3.50	High Level
3. were your concerns addressed by the school well?	3.82	High Level	3.50	High Level
4. are you still stressed with all these crises happening now?	3.76	High Level	3.55	High Level
5. do you still have a hard time coping with the daily demands in school and at home?	3.62	High Level	3.32	Moderate Level
6. is it better to conduct this type of learning now?	3.79	High Level	3.75	High Level
7. do you still feel depressed knowing that we will soon have face-to-face classes?	3.60	High Level	3.41	Moderate Level
8. are you stressed with the way the school is dealing with school concerns and issues?	3.59	High Level	3.33	Moderate Level
9. do you still have students struggling with anxiety over this present situation?	3.56	High Level	3.29	Moderate Level
10. are you more financially stressed now?	3.57	High Level	3.35	Moderate Level
Mean	3.67	High Level	3.45	Moderate Level

Table 11 exhibits the level of teachers' well-being in the Physiological Aspect when grouped according to highest educational attainment. The overall mean scores were 3.67 among the lower education achieved group interpreted as "high level" while 3.45 from the higher education achieved group interpreted as "moderate level." Item No. 3 got the highest mean score of 3.82 to lower education achieved groups, interpreted as "high level" while item no. 6 also obtained the highest mean score of 3.75 among the higher education achieved group also interpreted as "high level." Item no. 9 obtained the lowest mean scores of 3.56 to lower and 3.29 to higher education achieved group interpreted as "high and moderate level" respectively. The results imply that teachers' well-being towards their concerns was quite addressed well, so the implementation of this type of learning now helps struggling students with anxiety regarding their present situation. The implication affirms with Cann (2020) which states, a teacher's wellbeing has a significant impact on schools, teachers and students. Many of the negative effects of low wellbeing are well publicized, with stress or burnout being linked to attrition and the resulting teacher shortages worldwide and in New Zealand. This has led to calls for teacher wellbeing to be taken seriously for the long-term sustainability of the profession.

Table 12. Level of the Teachers' Well-being in the Social Aspect When Grouped According to Age

Items	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
Compared to before the COVID-19 pandemic...				
1. can you say that your workload has taken much of your time for the family?	3.51	High Level	3.46	Moderate Level
2. how was your relationship with your co-teachers now?	4.25	High Level	4.12	High Level
3. how was your relationship with your family now?	4.36	High Level	4.26	High Level
4. did the weekly meeting with your parents improve your relationship with them as you get to update them about their child/children's academic performance?	3.95	High Level	4.01	High Level
5. do you still have recreation time with your family now?	3.78	High Level	3.47	Moderate Level
6. are you more anxious of how your learners will feel when classes reopen on a face-to-face set up?	3.62	High Level	3.66	High Level
7. Do the schools' intervention plans help improve your well-being?	3.74	High Level	3.83	High Level
8. how is your teaching performance now?	4.01	High Level	4.08	High Level
9. how was your social life as a teacher?	3.62	High Level	3.74	High Level
10. does it affect your professional efficacy?	3.68	High Level	3.66	High Level
Mean	3.85	High Level	3.83	High Level

Table 12 presents the level of teachers' well-being in the Social Aspect when grouped according to age. The overall mean scores were 3.85 among the younger teacher respondents, while 3.83 among the older age group both interpreted as "high level." Item no. 3 got the highest mean scores of 4.36 and 4.26 to both younger and older age groups, interpreted as "high level," while item no. 1 got the lowest mean scores of 3.51 and 3.46 among both younger and older teacher respondents interpreted as "high and moderate levels" respectively. This implies that teachers socially felt that their relationship with their family is high. However, both age groups realized that their school work had jeopardized their time with the family. The implication confirms that of Alvarez et al (2021) who posit that it is important to understand that well-being is a complex construct that includes a variety of subjective indicators. Some of which are related to personal growth and self-actualization, which must always be considered in context. Research measuring teachers' psychological well-being has yielded interesting results. These may suggest guidelines for the development of psychosocial intervention strategies.

Table 13. Level of the Teachers' Well-being in the Social Aspect When Grouped According to Length of Service

Items	Shorter		Longer	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
Compared to before the COVID-19 pandemic...				
1. can you say that your workload has taken much of your time for the family?	3.46	Moderate Level	3.50	High Level
2. how was your relationship with your co-teachers now?	4.25	High Level	4.13	High Level
3. how was your relationship with your family now?	4.32	High Level	4.30	High Level
4. did the weekly meeting with your parents improve your relationship with them as you get to update them about their child/children's academic performance?	3.96	High Level	4.00	High Level
5. do you still have recreation time with your family now?	3.56	High Level	3.68	High Level
6. are you more anxious of how your learners will feel when classes reopen on a face-to-face set up?	3.62	High Level	3.65	High Level
7. Do the schools' intervention plans help improve your well-being?	3.70	High Level	3.86	High Level
8. how is your teaching performance now?	4.06	High Level	4.04	High Level
9. how was your social life as a teacher?	3.51	High Level	3.83	High Level
10. does it affect your professional efficacy?	3.60	High Level	3.72	High Level
Mean	3.80	High Level	3.87	High Level

Table 13 shows the level of teachers' well-being in the Social Aspect when grouped according to length of service. The overall mean scores were 3.80 among the shorter tenured group and 3.87 from the longer tenured group, both interpreted as "high level." Item No. 3, again got the highest mean scores of 4.32 and 4.30 to both tenured groups, interpreted as "high level." On the other hand, item no. 1, got the lowest mean scores of 3.46 and 3.50 to both tenured groups, interpreted as "moderate and high level" respectively. The results imply that teachers find their relationship with the family to a high level, which nurtures their healthy well-being, but their school work

seems to be a factor as assessed by teachers, which affects their well-being. The implication was confirmed by Dayagbil et al. (2021) in their survey, which included the type of home environment the students have to assess factors that influence their difficulty. Students were asked whether their home learning environment is conducive to learning or not. As teaching continuity was made possible through online modality and other home-based tasks, they still had difficulty complying with the requirements of the course.

Table 14. *Level of the Teachers' Well-being in the Social Aspect of When Grouped According to Average Family Monthly Income*

Items	Lower Mean	Interpretation	Higher Mean	Interpretation
Compared to before the COVID-19 pandemic...				
1. can you say that your workload has taken much of your time for the family?	3.42	Moderate Level	3.55	High Level
2. how was your relationship with your co-teachers now?	4.17	High Level	4.20	High Level
3. how was your relationship with your family now?	4.23	High Level	4.39	High Level
4. did the weekly meeting with your parents improve your relationship with them as you get to update them about their child/children's academic performance?	3.94	High Level	4.02	High Level
5. do you still have recreation time with your family now?	3.44	Moderate Level	3.81	High Level
6. are you more anxious of how your learners will feel when classes reopen on a face-to-face set up?	3.57	High Level	3.71	High Level
7. Do the schools' intervention plans help improve your well-being?	3.80	High Level	3.76	High Level
8. how is your teaching performance now?	4.01	High Level	4.08	High Level
9. how was your social life as a teacher?	3.48	Moderate Level	3.88	High Level
10. does it affect your professional efficacy?	3.63	High Level	3.71	High Level
Mean	3.77	High Level	3.91	High Level

Table 14 displays the level of teachers' well-being in the Social Aspect when grouped according to average family monthly income. The overall mean scores were 3.77 among the lower income group and 3.91 from the higher income group, both interpreted as "high level." Item No. 3, consistently got the highest mean score of 4.23 and 4.39 to both lower and higher income teacher respondents, both interpreted as "high level." Yet, item no. 1 obtained the lowest mean scores of 3.42 and 3.55 among the lower and higher income teachers both interpreted as "moderate and high levels" separately. The results imply that teachers show a harmonious relationship among their family members, but their school workload gets in the way, which takes much of your time from the family. The implication confirms with Wakui et al. (2021), which concerns teachers who have faced the prospect of going back to onsite teaching and have experienced anxiety about contagion risk as well as falling behind or having difficulty keeping up with the planned teaching schedule and overall student progress.

Table 15. *Level of the Teachers' Well-being in the Social Aspect When Grouped According to Highest Educational Attainment*

Items	Lower Mean	Interpretation	Higher Mean	Interpretation
Compared to before the COVID-19 pandemic...				
1. can you say that your workload has taken much of your time for the family?	3.53	High Level	3.44	Moderate Level
2. how was your relationship with your co-teachers now?	4.24	High Level	4.13	High Level
3. how was your relationship with your family now?	4.33	High Level	4.29	High Level
4. did the weekly meeting with your parents improve your relationship with them as you get to update them about their child/children's academic performance?	4.02	High Level	3.94	High Level
5. do you still have recreation time with your family now?	3.59	High Level	3.66	High Level
6. are you more anxious of how your learners will feel when classes reopen on a face-to-face set up?	3.68	High Level	3.60	High Level
7. Do the schools' intervention plans help improve your well-being?	3.89	High Level	3.67	High Level
8. how is your teaching performance now?	4.14	High Level	3.95	High Level
9. how was your social life as a teacher?	3.75	High Level	3.61	High Level
10. does it affect your professional efficacy?	3.73	High Level	3.60	High Level
Mean	3.89	High Level	3.79	High Level

Table 15 exhibits the level of teachers' well-being in the Social Aspect when grouped according to highest educational attainment. The overall mean scores were 3.89 among the lower education achieved group interpreted as "high level" while 3.79 from the higher education achieved group interpreted as "high level." Item No. 3 got the highest mean scores of 4.33 and 4.29 to both lower and higher education achieved groups, interpreted as "high level" while item no. 1 also obtained by both lower and higher education achieved group of 3.53 and 3.44 interpreted as "high and moderate levels" consecutively. The results imply that teachers' well-being towards their social aspect posts a high level when interrelationship among family members is concerned but the school tasks impedes it all. The implication affirms that teachers' well-being is a complex construct, which has been conceptualized as the absence of negative conditions such as teacher's stress, demotivation and even burnout (García-Álvarez D, Soler MJ and Achard-Braga L., 2021).

Table 16. *Difference in the Level of the Teachers' Well-being in the Psychological Aspect of When Grouped and Compared According to the Aforementioned Variables*

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	66	67.12	2219.000	0.592		Not Significant
	Older	71	70.75				
Highest Educational Attainment Length of service	Lower	69	70.12	2269.000	0.740	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	68	67.87				
	Shorter	64	70.83	2219.000	0.613		Not Significant
	Longer	73	67.40				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	68	65.77	2126.500	0.344		Not Significant
	Higher	69	72.18				

Table 16 shows no significant difference in the level of Teachers' Well-being in the Psychological Aspect when grouped and compared according to variables. This implies that the variables age, highest educational attainment, length of service, average family monthly income, and net pay do not significantly affect the level of teachers' well-being in the Psychological Aspect. This implication negates Zhou and Yao's (2020) study, where findings reveal significant differences in family income that are attributable to harmonious relationships of teachers and is important to support them psychologically.

Table 17. *Difference in the Level of the Teachers' Well-being in the Physiological Aspect When Grouped and Compared According to the Aforementioned Variables*

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	66	67.55	2247.500	0.680		Not Significant
	Older	71	70.35				
Highest Educational Attainment Length of service	Lower	69	75.40	1904.500	0.057	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	68	62.51				
	Shorter	64	69.82	2283.500	0.821		Not Significant
	Longer	73	68.28				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	68	67.28	2229.000	0.614		Not Significant
	Higher	69	70.70				

Table 17 shows no significant difference in the level of Teachers' Well-being in the Physiological Aspect when grouped and compared according to variables. This implies that the variables age, highest educational attainment, length of service, average family monthly income, and net pay do not significantly affect the level of teachers' well-being in the Physiological Aspect. Camino (2021) also negates this implication as in his study found out that length of experience in teaching is inversely but significantly related to the values candor, colleague, organizational pride and teamwork.

Table 18. Difference in the Level of the Teachers' Well-being in the Social Aspect When Grouped and Compared According to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	66	70.69	2231.500	0.630	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	71	67.43				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	69	71.85	2149.500	0.397	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	68	66.11				
Length of service	Shorter	64	66.95	2205.000	0.571	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer	73	70.79				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	68	63.84	1995.000	0.130	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	69	74.09				

Table 18 shows no significant difference in the level of Teachers' Well-being in the Social Aspect when grouped and compared according to variables. This implies that the variables age, highest educational attainment, length of service, average family monthly income and net pay does not significantly affect the level of teachers' well-being in the Social Aspect. This implication negates the findings of Camino (2021), which shows that women in their 40s scored significantly higher on anger while at work compared to women from other age groups; however, it also showed no significant age differences were found in anger experienced at home.

Conclusions

With these findings, it is concluded that most of the teacher respondents are older and have served the school longer and earned a higher salary, but need to improve their Bachelor's Degree as they already have a better net pay. Therefore, psychologically, teachers feel conscious and worried while they attend meetings, and they find their situation miserable. Physiologically, students are stressed with apprehension over this present situation. Socially, teachers' job has taken much of their time for their family. Based on the conclusions, these recommendations were formulated: 1) School Heads should encourage their teachers to take postgraduate studies to improve their status and educational advancement; 2) Teachers should address their concerns to their School Heads to assess the reasons why they feel worried and stressed during meetings and to have consultation time with teachers about why they think that their situation is miserable; 3) Consult teachers about why they are stressed and anxious about their current situation to formally address their needs and concerns; and 4) Retraining on time management and classroom management that the school must practice to promote a healthy well-being of teachers.

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